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Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

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Narzieva Dilfuza Bakhtiyorovna
Samarkand State Medical University
Radjabiy Muzaayanna Aziz kizi
Tashkent State Dental Institute

IMPROVING THE TREATMENT OF PERI-IMPLANTITIS USING THE HERBAL MEDICINE ZUB-PRE

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ANNOTATION

This article analyzes and carefully studies the characteristic features of peri-implant fluid and saliva in 42 patients with class I and II peri-implantitis. In the main group, we used rinsing with the herbal medicine Zub-Pre to treat patients, and in the compared group, treatment of peri-implantitis was carried out based on traditional surgical methods. According to the results of the study, in the immediate period after treatment of peri-implantitis, we found that in the main group, 93% of patients, when using complex treatment of peri-implantitis using the herbal medicine Zub-Pre, already on the 2nd day experienced a significant improvement in well-being, reduction in swelling and subsidence of pain in the postoperative area fields. In the compared group, in 80% of patients the pain syndrome lasted more than 3 days.

Key words: dental implantation, peri-implantitis, herbal medicine Zub-Pre.

Нарзиева Дилфуза Бахтиёрвна
Самаркандский государственный
медицинский университет
Раджабий Музаевна Азиз кизи
Ташкентский государственный
стоматологический институт

УСОСЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПЕРИИМПЛАНТИТА С ПОМОЩЬЮ ФИТОПРЕПАРАТА ZUB-PRE

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье проанализированы и тщательно изучены характерные особенности периимплантатной жидкости и слюны у 42 больных с периимплантатами I и II класса. В основной группе для лечения пациентов мы использовали полоскание фитопрепаратом Zub-Pre, а в сравниваемой группе лечение периимплантита проводилось на основе традиционных хирургических методов. По результатам исследования в ближайшие сроки после лечения периимплантитов мы обнаружили, что в основной группе у 93% пациентов при применении комплексного лечения периимплантитов с использованием фитопрепарата Zub-Pre уже на 2-е сутки наблюдалось значительное улучшение самочувствия, уменьшение отеков и утихание болей в области послеоперационного поля. В сравниваемой группе, у 80% больных болевой синдром продолжался более 3 суток.

Ключевые слова: дентальная имплантация, периимплантит, фитопрепарат Zub-Pre.

Narzieva Dilfuza Baxtiyorovna
Samarqand davlati tibbiyot universiteti
Radjabiy Muzaayanna Aziz qizi
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

PERI-IMPLANTITLARNI DAVOLASHNI ZUB-PRE FITOPREPARATI YORDAMIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

ANNOTATSIIYA

Ushbu maqolada I va II sinf peri-implantit tashxisi qo'yilgan 42 bemorda peri-implant bo'shlig'i suyuqligi va so'lakning xarakterli xususiyatlari tahlil qilindi va diqqat bilan o'rganildi. Asosiy guruhda bemorlarni davolash uchun, fitopreparat Zub-Pre bilan chayishdan foydalandik va taqqoslangan guruhda peri-implantitni davolash an'anaviy jarrohlik usullari asosida amalga oshirildi. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, peri-implantitni davolashdan so'ng, biz aniqladikki, asosiy guruhda bemorlarning 93 foizi peri-implantitni kompleks davolashda Zub-Pre fitopreparatidan foydalanganda 2-kuni bemorlar umumiy axvolini sezilarli yaxshilanishi, operatsiyadan keyingi sohalarda shish va og'riqning kamayishi kuzatildi. Taqqoslangan guruhda bemorlarning 80 foizida og'riq sindromi 3 kundan ortiq davom etgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tish implantatsiyasi, peri-implantit, fitopreparat Zub-Pre.

Relevance. A major achievement in dentistry is the widespread introduction into practice of a relatively new promising area - implantology. The essence of implantology is the introduction of a titanium implant of various designs into bone tissue. Data from some international authors claim that approximately 45 to 65% of the population around the world need dental prosthetics, and generally the age of those in need ranges from 35-45 years, while women have a 20% higher need for dental prosthetics. The main goal of dental implantology, in addition to restoring lost teeth, is also the restoration of the integrity of the dentition along with the full restoration of the chewing function and aesthetic appearance of each patient. Postoperative complications associated with trauma from wound damage and aseptic inflammation (peri-implantitis) remain at a high level [1; 2]. Thus, inflammatory complications after dental implantation range from 10 to 40%, while manifestations of inflammation are often asymptomatic for patients and are detected during clinical and radiological examination. The frequency of inflammatory complications attracts the attention of implantologists to the problem of prevention and treatment of mucositis and peri-implantitis [3]. One of the promising areas in modern restorative medicine is the creation of new, more effective non-drug methods of therapeutic measures that would significantly increase the functional reserves of both healthy and sick people [1; 4]. As you know, the flora of Uzbekistan is rich in plants that have a wide range of medicinal effects.

Purpose of the study. Studying the effectiveness of using the herbal medicine Zub-pre in the treatment of peri-implantitis.

Materials and methods of research. To conduct the study, we selected 42 patients who experienced peri-implantitis after dental implantation and divided them into 2 groups: the main group and the comparison group. In the main group, patients were also treated with surgical methods (curettage, removal of granulation tissue, antibiotics), but rinsing with the herbal medicine Zub-pre was additionally prescribed. In the compared group, treatment of peri-implantitis was carried out on the basis of traditional surgical methods of treatment without additional prescription. When conducting our research, we adhered to the S.A. classification. Jovanovika (1990), who divides the severity of inflammation into the following groups: 1st class - inflammation of peri-implant soft tissues (mucositis); 2nd class - mucositis with a soft horizontal or vertical bone defect at 1/5 of the length of the implant located in the bone; 3rd class - mucositis with a moderate horizontal or vertical bone defect at 1/3 of the length of the implant located in the bone; Class 4 - mucositis with a severe horizontal or vertical bone defect of more than 1/3 of the length of the implant located in the bone. During the study, the Fedorov-Volodkina hygienic index, the papillary-marginal-alveolar index (PMA) were studied, the Schiller-Pisarev test was performed, the periodontal Russell index and the pH of the oral fluid were determined, and a cytological study of the gingival fluid was performed.

Research results and discussion. When conducting clinical laboratory examinations in the immediate period after treatment of peri-implantitis, we found that in the main group, 93% of patients, when using complex treatment using the herbal medicine Zub-pre, already experienced a significant improvement in well-being by 2.1 ± 0.9 days, a decrease in swelling and subsidence pain in the postoperative area. This can be explained by the fact that the use of the herbal medicine Zub-pre in the area of surgical intervention has an anti-edematous, bactericidal, analgesic effect, and also significantly enhances the regenerative and reparative functions of the body. In the compared group, in 80% of patients the pain syndrome lasted 3.2 ± 0.21 days, which is slightly longer than in the main group ($P > 0.05$). In the main group, the average time for edema relief was 4.3 ± 0.36 days, and in the comparison group 6.1 ± 0.27 days ($P < 0.05$). Body temperature in the comparison group normalized only by 1.9 ± 0.8 days ($P < 0.05$), and in patients of the main group by 1.1 ± 0.2 days. The healing time of the mucous membrane in the two clinical groups was 8.3 ± 1.2 days in the main group, and 10.6 ± 2.1 days in the comparison group, respectively. For complete elimination of inflammatory phenomena, it took 8.9 ± 1.9 days in the main group, and 12.2 ± 2.4 days in the comparison group ($P < 0.05$). The results of our study also revealed positive dynamics in indicators of local reactivity of the body due to the combined treatment

of patients. Thus, in the main study group, the absolute number of neutrophils in 1 ml of mixed saliva was higher than in patients of the comparison group. At the same time, in the main group there was a pronounced tendency towards normalization of the number of neutrophils in saliva. In the compared group, with the traditional method of treatment, there was also a tendency towards normalization of the number of neutrophils, but in a less pronounced form. Based on this, in the main study group there is a noticeable difference in the dynamics of normalization of the number of neutrophils. When comparing the results, after a quantitative assessment of peri-implant fluid and saliva in patients with peri-implantitis, there is a significant increase in the volume of epithelial cells compared to the norm. Along with this, compared with healthy people, patients with class 1 peri-implantitis show an increase in the content of epithelial cells in saliva - 5.1 ± 0.9 and 1.7 ± 0.1 ($p < 0.001$) and in peri-implant fluid - 4.8 ± 0.5 3 times in relation to gingival fluid - 1.6 ± 0.3 ($p < 0.001$). In patients with a more severe course of peri-implantitis (class 2) compared to healthy people, there is only a slight difference in the content of epithelial cells in these environments and is 4.9 ± 0.3 and 1.7 ± 0.1 in saliva ($p < 0.001$), in the peri-implant fluid - 4.1 ± 0.2 compared to gingival fluid 1.6 ± 0.3 ($p < 0.001$). This phenomenon indicates the formation of the body's protective function in response to the inflammatory process, so the difference in this case was not so significant, whereas with class 1 peri-implantitis, the body's protective functions were not yet activated, and therefore the difference in indicators was significant. In the main group, on the 5th day of treatment for both class 1 and class 2 peri-implantitis, normalization of the number of epithelial cells in both saliva and peri-implant fluid was noted. In the comparison group, relative normalization of these same indicators occurs only after a month. When examining the leukocyte content in saliva and peri-implant fluid, patients with peri-implantitis definitely experience an increase in the number of leukocytes compared to the norm. Thus, with class 1 peri-implantitis, the number of leukocytes in the peri-implant fluid is 5.0 ± 0.6 , while at normal levels in the gingival fluid it is 1.2 ± 0.2 ($p < 0.01$), in saliva - 3.1 ± 0.4 with a norm of 0.9 ± 0.1 . Based on the results obtained, it was found that patients with peri-implantitis have an increased number of leukocytes both in the peri-implant fluid and in saliva, which characterizes the presence of an inflammatory process. In the main group, on the 5th day of treatment in patients with class 1 peri-implantitis, there was a significant decrease, to normal levels, in the number of leukocytes and epithelial cells in both the peri-implant fluid and saliva. Also, in these patients, the cytological picture is completely restored, which is characterized by an increase in mature forms of epithelial cells up to 91%, which practically corresponds to the indicators of healthy individuals. In the compared group of patients with class 1 peri-implantitis, although there was a certain decrease in the number of leukocytes and epithelial cells both in the peri-implant fluid and in saliva, they still differed significantly from normal values. Thus, the number of mature epithelial cells (6th degree of maturity) was 57%, while these results differ significantly from the cytological indicators of healthy individuals and from the results obtained in the main group. In patients of the compared group with peri-implantitis of the 2nd class, there was also a tendency for cytological indicators to improve, but compared to the main group they were less significant in terms of both quantitative and qualitative indicators ($p < 0.05$). After the course of treatment, in patients with class 1 peri-implantitis in the main group, the quantitative and qualitative indicators of epithelial cells and leukocytes in the peri-implant fluid and saliva were completely restored to the level of healthy individuals. In the same category of patients in the comparison group, after treatment with traditional methods, there was also a decrease in the number of epithelial cells and leukocytes in the studied biological media ($p < 0.05$), only in this case the indicators were almost 2 times higher than in the main group, and significantly exceeded the values of healthy individuals. The most noticeable difference in the indicators of the compared group in relation to the main group of subjects was identified in the differentiation of epithelial cells, since the increase in the number of mature forms of epithelial cells in the compared group was noted only by 17%, while in the main group it was 91%. A month after the treatment, in patients of the main group with 1st and 2nd class peri-implantitis, in 100% and 98.2% of cases,

respectively, the inflammatory process in the gums was stopped, and the gums were in a healthy state. Only 1.8% of patients in the main group with class II peri-implantitis still had symptoms of mild gingivitis. In the compared group, in patients with class I and class 2 peri-implantitis, the effectiveness of treatment was 92% and 80%, respectively, in these cases the gums were healthy, and in the remaining 8% of patients with class I peri-implantitis and in 20% of patients with class II peri-implantitis, gingivitis symptoms persisted. It follows that 1 month after treatment of peri-implantitis, the hygienic state of the oral cavity in patients of the main group is significantly better than in the comparison group. Thus, in the main group, patients with class I peri-implantitis were cured in 100% of cases, while in the comparison group, patients

with the same class of peri-implantitis required further re-treatment in 8% of cases.

Conclusion. Thus, the use of the herbal medicine Zub-pre in the treatment of patients with class I and II peri-implantitis can significantly increase the effectiveness of surgical treatment methods. This is explained by the fact that anise decoction has an antibacterial, anti-inflammatory effect, accelerates the regenerative and reparative functions of the body, which affects the formation of a mature bone structure in the area of the defect, thereby increasing the strength of implant fixation. As a result, this is reflected in long-term results due to more effective relief of the inflammatory process in the early stages.

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